

Erroneous references in the commentary by Wang et al. (2024)

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Comment on:

Wang C, Sun Z, Zhou W.

A commentary on ‘Efficacy and safety of vitamin C for atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: a meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials’.

Int J Surg. 2024 Jul 1;110(7):4416-4417.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38445473>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11254203>

<https://doi.org/10.1097/js9.0000000000001269>

Wang et al. [1] write that “*Hu et al.[2] performed a meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials on patients undergoing heart surgery who received vitamin C.*”

However, the Hu et al. paper was shown to be flawed [3]. For example, “Hu et al. stated in their methods that ‘*studies that met the following criteria were included: randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of adult patients who underwent cardiac surgery; patients randomly assigned to receive vitamin C or placebo ... Any studies of non-randomized designs ... were excluded*’.

However, Hu included the study by Carnes et al. although that was not an RCT” [3] and “In their Fig. 4, Hu et al. stated that the standard deviation (SD) of the mean duration of ICU stay in the vitamin C group was 24.9 hours in the trial by Colby et al. However, Colby reported in their Table 1 and text that the SD for the duration of ICU stay was 249.9 hours in their vitamin C group, i.e. 10 times greater than Hu claimed” [3].

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

Wang et al. also write: “*Subsequent trials ought to concentrate more intently on outcomes that impact long-term and patient-relevant outcomes, like organ dysfunction, quality of life, discharge location, and ability to return to work [4].*”

However, this study [4] was also shown to be flawed [5]. For example, “The abstract states that ‘*vitamin C significantly decreased ... ventilation time ($p < 0.00001$)*’. We believe that this conclusion is incorrect based on the evidence presented. This particularly small p-value from Figure 6 is associated with the test of heterogeneity, not with the test of overall effect ($p = 0.02$, $Z = 2.27$). In the abstract, this same error occurs for ICU length of stay and hospital length of stay in that the reported p-values are from the heterogeneity tests, not from the tests of overall effect. Furthermore, Hill states in Figure 6 that the ventilation time in the Safaei trial was 15.1 h with 1.0 h standard deviation (SD) in the vitamin C group and 22.9 h (SD 3.8 h) in the control group. These dispersion estimates were published by Safaei, however, as standard errors (SE) and not SDs” [5].

References

1. Wang C, Sun Z, Zhou W. A commentary on ‘Efficacy and safety of vitamin C for atrial fibrillation after cardiac surgery: a meta-analysis with trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials’. *Int J Surg.* 2024 Jul 1;110(7):4416-4417.
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